

REVISITING KONRAD WACHSMANN'S DYNAMIC STRUCTURE: GEOMETRY, STRUCTURAL FEASIBILITY, AND CONSTRUCTABILITY

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ABSTRACT

In 1953, Konrad Wachsmann proposed the dynamic structure (DS) for designing a rigid-frame structure comprising a single structural element. To reduce the environmental footprint and save resources and construction materials, translating a complex structure into constructible shapes, such as DS, is crucial for rationalizing the construction. This paper validates Wachsmann's idea and presents an updated design methodology for obtaining a geometry close to the DS with structural and constructible feasibility. First, the geometry of DS is reproduced according to the previous literature by using 3D CAD. Through observing the reproduced model, a revised algorithm and a new layout are proposed for improving structural and constructive performance. Furthermore, both an observation for obtained geometry and a linear static finite element (FE) analysis are conducted to investigate its structural feasibility. Finally, the effectiveness of the proposed method and the possibility of the application of DS are discussed.

Keywords: conceptual design, morphology, three-dimensional computer-aided design, finite element analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Konrad Wachsmann attempted to design buildings considering the joinery of building components and effective mass production of building elements. For example, a general panel house, where standard wooden panels and universal metal connectors are used for connections, and the U.S. Air Force aircraft hangar, which comprises prefabricated modularized truss bars and nodes, are representative of Wachsmann's designs. In 1953, he proposed the dynamic structure (DS) for designing a rigid-frame structure comprising a single structural element. Fig. 1 shows the conceptual image of the DS. As seen in Fig.1, Blue and red solid elements (hereafter called universal elements) are rotationally assembled to form column-like units (basic units). Green-colored solid elements (sub-beams) connect between basic units. It is remarkable that the typology of the joints of DS differed significantly from Wachsmann's previous design. The place where column-and-beam

Figure 1: Conceptual image of DS [1].

Figure 2: Cross sections of universal elements [1].

joints of the conventional rigid frame are located is a void. According to his study, the shape of the universal element can be designed by considering stress conditions. Besides, it indicates the structural topology, and various cross-sections are available as shown in Fig. 2. A configuration of DS overcomes the monotony of repetitively constructed systems that prefabricated frames tend to have. However, due to the complex joints, the properties of DS (e.g., geometrical configuration, the construction procedure, or the mechanical behavior of a system composed of members in a rotational arrangement) are difficult to evaluate intuitively. Wachsman didn't evaluate these properties in his study. Fig. 3 (a) illustrates Wachsman's image of the prefabricated elements composed of DS and installations. Fig. 3 (b) shows the erection sequence. Wachsman designed the whole structure to be constructed by assembling and stacking basic units and sub-beams. As seen in Fig. 3 (a), environmental material and equipment, such as piping, indicated by red arrows, is encapsulated in the basic unit.

Figure 3: Completely prefabricated building element with DS and installations (a), and erection sequence (b).

A previous study on the history of prefabricated panelized housing [2] indicated that prefabricated wall panels have played a significant role in improving both environmental performance and construction ease. In recent years, as sustainable design has gained popularity, more equipment is being installed in the voids within the walls and ceilings of buildings in order to improve

environmental performance. Piping and wiring for facilities run through buildings in an increasingly complex manner, making it more difficult to integrate them with the structure. DS, which provides voids within the structure, can integrate that equipment for better environmental performance.

Furthermore, recent developments in digital design tools, such as three-dimensional (3D) computer-aided design (CAD) and engineering (CAE), and digital fabrication techniques, enable the design of complex shapes. Computational form-finding allows the design of complicated architectural images as mechanically rationalized structures for practical designs [3, 4]. However, the construction of complex shapes tends to increase costs or cause waste of construction materials. Environmental footprints and saving resources have become increasingly important topics. Previous studies have attempted to obtain optimal shapes with construction efficiency using numerical methods [5-8]. However, few studies have obtained structural forms limited to one or a few kinds of member patterns. Although recent studies and practical examples demonstrate the use of digital fabrication to manufacture multiple patterns of parts, if we can design and manufacture complex shapes comprising a single or a few components, we can expect further improvements in workability for construction. Totally, it can be considered that the designing approach for DS has the possibility of rationalizing both structural engineering, construction, and environmental performance.

Few recent studies have focused on the DS. Enright investigated the DS by reproducing 3D structures [9]. Considering Wachsman's algorithm, Burkhalter et al. developed a 3D model named grapevine structure (GS). A single-story wooden sculpture extracted from the shape of GS was modeled and exhibited at the Biennale Venice, 2018 [10, 11]. However, to date, the mechanical properties of the DS have not been fully studied. The mechanical behavior of existing buildings (or already demolished buildings) designed by distinguished architects or engineers has been investigated to explore their design concepts [12-14]. The authors think that investigating the mechanical properties of a DS can provide insights into its architectural applications.

In this study, the possibility of architectural applications of the DS is explored from a structural engineering perspective. Firstly, we reproduce the original DS using the 3D CAD software, namely

Rhinoceros and Grasshopper, following a previous study [1] (Section 2). Then, we propose an improved design algorithm and assembling procedure for the DS (Sections 3.1 and 3.2). Furthermore, we conduct the linear static FE analysis to investigate the mechanical properties of the obtained DS using the revised algorithm and assembling procedure (Section 3.3). Finally, the possibility of application of the DS is discussed. This paper validates past innovative ideas using current CAD/CAE technologies and presents an updated design methodology for obtaining a geometry close to the original shape with structural and constructible feasibility.

2. DIGITAL MODELING OF WACHSMAN'S STRUCTURE

As mentioned in Section 1, the basic units of the DS can be obtained by rotationally duplicating universal elements. Section 2.1 introduces the generating procedure for basic units, and Section 2.2 presents the assembling method using these units.

Figure 4: Universal element: vertical component (green), horizontal component (blue), and joint element (red).

Figure 5: Basic units: X-shape (left), and I-shape (right).

2.1. Universal elements and basic units

According to Wachsman's study, a universal element (Fig. 4) is generated first. Then, the basic unit (X-shape, Fig. 5(a)) is subsequently obtained by duplicating the universal elements. Note that the same procedure can be employed to obtain another pattern (I-shape, Fig. 5(b)). Fig. 6 shows the

generating procedure for basic units. It can be summarized as follows,

Step 1 Create a cube A with a length of x m. In this paper, $x = 4$ m according to the previous study [1].

Step 2 Project six squares $B_1 - B_6$ with a length of y m onto the centroid of each face of A .

Step 3 Extrude using $B_1 - B_6$ to make three rectangular solids $C_1 - C_3$.

Step 4 Create a cube D by intersecting $C_1 - C_3$ obtained in Step 3.

Step 5 Create a new cube E with a side of $y' = y/\sqrt{2}$ m.

Step 6 Create a new cube F by rotating E by 45 degrees.

Step 7 Divide a top surface and a side of F into $s_1 \times s_2$ pieces. On each face, select one of the divided faces.

Step 8 Draw two arcs. Create the joint element, as shown in red in Fig. 3, using the two surfaces created in Step 7.

Step 9 Create a strip G onto A with the same height as E .

Step 10 Choose one surface from G . Then divide the surface into $t_1 \times t_2$ rectangular faces and select two from them.

Step 11 Create the horizontal component, as shown in blue in Fig.3, using faces created in Steps 7 and 10.

Step 12 Project the top surface of E onto the top surface of A .

Step 13 Divide the surface created in Step 12 into $u_1 \times u_2$ rectangular faces and select one face from them.

Step 14 Create the vertical component, as shown in green in Fig. 3, using faces created in Steps 7 and 13. Join the components to create a universal element L .

Step 15 Rotate and duplicate L by 90 degrees around the centroid of A .

Step 16 With the centroid of A , duplicate the units obtained in Step 15 vertically and symmetrically. Finally, the basic unit for the DS in X-shape can be obtained. Note that if the units obtained in Step 15 are duplicated with the centroid of the top surface of A in the same manner, I-shaped basic units can be obtained.

Figure 6: Generating procedure for basic units.

As seen in Fig. 6, it can be found that his design method is compatible with computer algorithms. Note that the joint element can be controlled by varying y , s_1 , and s_2 . The horizontal and vertical components depend on t_1 , t_2 , u_1 , and u_2 . Herein, the parameters are assigned following values: $y = 1$ m, $s_1 = 4$, $s_2 = 2$, $t_1 = 6$, $t_2 = 4$, and $u_1 = u_2 = 4$. In Section 3.1, we propose a revised Step 8 to obtain the joint component of basic units.

2.2. Assembling basic units

Figs. 7 (a) and 8 (a) show the original layout to form the DS (Planar parallel layout). Basic units S+ are arranged at constant intervals. Tilted sub-beams are connected. According to a previous study [9], the sub-beam can be arranged diagonally (Diagonal spatial layout), as shown in Figs. 7 (b) and 8 (b), to create a flat surface above these beams.

Figure 7: Arrangement of basic units: (a) Planar parallel layout, and (b) Diagonal spatial layout.

Figure 8: Elevation views with two units and two layers: (a) Planar parallel layout and (b) Diagonal spatial layout.

2.3. Issues to be addressed for DS

Fig. 9 (a) shows an enlarged view of the X-shape. Fig. 9 (b) depicts Step 8 extracted from the generation process shown in Fig. 6. As seen in Fig. 9, the upper and lower universal elements are in contact with a small area due to a fan-like joint element, which is obtained in Step 8. Considering a practical design, a sufficient joint area is needed to connect each unit to transmit internal stress properly. Fig. 10 shows the shape of the GS, which is obtained according to a previous study [10].

Figure 9: Enlarged view of DS in X-shape: (a) joint for upper and lower universal elements and (b) diagram of Step 8 in the generation process.

Figure 10: Enlarged view of GS in X-shape: (a) joint for upper and lower units and (b) joint element in the generation procedure.

In this case, vertical and horizontal components are connected directly. It can be considered that sufficient stress transmission is hard to realize because both universal elements are separated.

3. INVESTIGATION FOR DS

As shown in Section 2, a sufficient joint area is needed to connect universal elements in X-shape. We propose a revised algorithm for connecting both upper and lower universal elements to realize smooth stress transmission. Furthermore, we propose an improved assembling procedure that enables the appropriate connection of sub-beams.

3.1. Improved algorithm for the basic units

This paper revises Step 8 (Step 8'). It can be expressed as follows,

Figure 11: Diagram of Step 8': (a) a face divided new surface H into $v_1 \times v_2$ faces, (b) obtained joint component.

Step 8' Divide F into two parts at the top and bottom and create a new surface H between them. Furthermore, divide H into $v_1 \times v_2$ faces and select one from them. Form a joint component from the divided face and two faces created in Step 7.

Fig. 11 shows the diagram of Step 8', where the obtained shape of a revised joint component is shown in red. The joint area can be varied by controlling v_1 and v_2 . We set $v_1 = v_2 = 4$.

3.2. Improved assembling procedure

This paper also proposes an improved assembling procedure, which allows basic units, described as $S+$ and $S-$, to be arranged in a mirror-reversal manner. Fig. 12 represents a new DS layout (Mirror-reversal layout) with two units and two layers. Stacked basic units are linearly symmetrical with black dotted lines, as shown in Fig. 12 (a). It can be found that, unlike Planar parallel and Diagonal spatial layouts, straightened sub-beams connect with stacked basic units horizontally, as shown in Fig. 12 (b).

Figure 12: Mirror-reversal layout: (a) basic units in a mirror-reversal manner, (b) elevation view with two units and two layers.

3.3. Validation of revised DS

3.3.1 Observation of DS's geometry

Firstly, we observe the basic unit, which is obtained by the revised algorithm. Fig. 13 shows an enlarged view of obtained shapes, in which the upper and lower universal elements are highlighted with red and blue colors, respectively. Fig. 14 shows the 3D-printed model. As seen in Figs. 13 and 14, it can be confirmed that a significant connection between the upper and lower universal elements is obtained compared with the shapes of the original DS and GS.

Figure 13: Enlarged views of obtained shape by revised algorithm.

Figure 14: Physical model of obtained shape by revised algorithm.

Figure 15: Dimensions of void in basic unit.

Figure 16: Comparison regarding layout of sub-beam: (a) Planar parallel layout and (b) Mirror-reversal layouts.

Fig. 15 shows the dimensions of the void in the basic unit. Note that the cross-sectional dimension at the end of the universal element is $B \times D = 333 \times 176$ (mm). Unlike conventional rigid frame structures, where piping cannot penetrate without “damaging” the structural element, the void has enough space to include equipment, such as piping. It could be integrated with both structural and environmental material and equipment design.

Fig. 16 represents the comparison regarding the layout of the sub-beam. As seen in Fig. 16, it can be considered that, in the Planar parallel layout, temporary shoring for supporting sub-beams is difficult and needs additional temporary braces to resist lateral force because tilted sub-beams are connected. Contrary to this, Diagonal spatial and Mirror-reversal layouts enable placing the sub-beam horizontally. It can be considered that these layouts can avoid the difficulty in temporary support for sub-beams.

3.3.2 Mechanical properties of universal elements

In this paper, the linear static FE analysis is conducted for the obtained geometry to evaluate its mechanical properties simply. MIDAS iGen, a general FE analysis software, is used. In this example, we assigned steel as the structural material because DS is applicable to steel elements with various cross-sectional shapes, as seen in Fig. 2. Furthermore, steel elements were used in previous Wachsmann’s works (a general house and the US Air Force aircraft hangar). Although DS is applicable to members with any kind of cross-sectional shape, as mentioned in Section 1, we directly assigned a box-shaped cross-section, which can be obtained from the generating procedure for basic units in Sections 2.1 and 3.1, to simplify the FE analysis. Firstly, we investigate jointed universal elements with hollow-core tube sections obtained by the revised generation procedure as shown in Fig. 17. The upper and lower universal elements are adhesively connected. The

obtained geometry is discretized into planar shell elements with a thickness of 6 mm. The material is steel with Young’s modulus of 205 GPa, Poisson’s ratio of 0.3, and density of 7.85 ton/m^3 . Self-weight is assigned as the external load. The bottom surface of ω_1 is pin supported. The top surface of ω_4 , and boundaries (ω_2 and ω_3) that are to be interconnected with other universal elements are constrained in the x and y directions.

Figure 17: FE model for universal elements.

Figure 18: Distribution of deformation (magnified by 300 times).

Table 1: Reaction forces R_x and R_y at ω_1 – ω_4 .

	R_x	R_y
ω_4	-	0.247
ω_3	-1.82	-0.486
ω_2	-	-0.546
ω_1	1.93	0.785

Unit: kN

Figure 19: Distribution of von Mises stress.

Figure 20: Construction procedure of basic unit.

Note that it can be considered universal elements can be composed of plates such as steel sheets or wooden plywood because the outer surface of the universal elements can be expressed as a swept surface generated by moving a line along two lines. Fig. 18 shows displacement distribution, in which it is magnified by 300 times. Grey lines represent the shape before deformation. The maximum displacements in the x , y , and z directions can be enumerated as 0.26, 0.39, and 0.36 mm, respectively. Table 1 lists the reaction forces at ω_1 – ω_4 . Note that the total weight of the model is approximately 4.60 kN. As shown in Fig. 18 and Table 1, it can be found that lateral deformation and reaction force occur due to the rotational arrangement of irregularly shaped elements. A lateral tensile force of 1.82 kN in the x -direction can be observed in the domain of ω_3 . This lateral tensile stress can be transmitted to each universal element via wet joints, such as fillet welding; The shear strength per length of fillet welding for a plate of 6 mm thickness is calculated to be 288 kN/m ($= 90.5 \text{ N/mm}^2 \times 4.5/\sqrt{2} \text{ mm}$) based on the design specifications [15]. Since the

total length of the intersection is measured as 0.885 m, allowable strength can be calculated as 254 kN ($> 1.82 \text{ kN}$).

Fig. 19 shows the distribution of von Mises stress in universal elements, with a maximum stress of 6.54 N/mm^2 in the joint between the upper and lower basic units. Conventional steel, which has a tensile strength of $F=400 \text{ N/mm}^2$, can be considered in this example. Allowable tensile stress in the long term can be calculated as $f_t=157 \text{ N/mm}^2$ [15]. As seen in Fig. 19, von Mises stress has a significantly smaller value than f_t . This result indicates that the obtained shape by the revised algorithm has sufficient areas for joining universal elements.

In any case, unlike a conventional rigid frame structure (built in the order of columns, beams, upper story columns...), the construction of the basic unit must be preceded by the construction of the whole structure. Fig. 20 depicts the possible construction procedure of the basic unit. The numbers indicate the construction steps. As seen in Fig. 18, Table 1, and Fig. 19, lateral deformation and reaction force subjected to their weight occur in a universal element due to its complex shape and supporting conditions during the assembly process. It can be considered that temporary supports and braces, which restrain both vertical and horizontal displacements, are needed during the construction phase for basic units, as shown in Fig. 20.

3.3.3 Mechanical properties of DS

FE analyses for three layouts (Planar parallel, Diagonal spatial, and Mirror reversal layouts) are also performed to investigate the effect of different layouts on mechanical performance. All FE models have four basic units in a 6-m interval in the x – y plane. Sub-beams with a length of 2 m are supported by basic units. Similar to the previous numerical example, basic units and sub-beams are discretized into planar shell elements with a thickness of 6 mm, and steel is considered as the structural material. Self-weight is assigned as the external load. Fig. 21 shows the FE model for the Mirror reversal layout. The bottom of the basic units is pinned supported. Notably, intersections of the basic units and joints between the basic unit and sub-beam are assumed to be rigid connections. Furthermore, the simple steel rigid frame system (Reference model), as shown in Figs. 22 and 23, is also validated for comparison. This model is discretized into a 3D beam element. H-shaped steel beams and tubular steel columns are assigned.

Figure 21: FE model for Mirror reversal layout: (a) plan, and (b) elevation view.

Figure 22: FE model for Reference model: (a) plan, and (b) elevation view.

Figure 23: Detail of beam-column connections in the Reference model: plan view (left), and elevation view (right).

As seen in Fig. 23, unlike the DS, the Reference model needs to be divided into three kinds of components (beams, columns, and beam-column connections). Note that the total weight values in the three layouts and the Reference model are approximately the same. It can be summarized as 89.1, 90.9, 88.8, and 89.0 (kN), respectively. Fig. 24 shows the displacement distribution, where d_{\max} , d_{xymax} , and d_{zmax} represent the maximum values of the root sum square of displacements in the x , y , and z directions, maximum absolute value of the lateral displacement and vertical displacement, respectively. As seen in Fig. 24, the values of d_{\max} , d_{xymax} , and d_{zmax} in the Mirror-reversal layout are approximately equal to the Planar parallel layout. Besides, compared to the Diagonal spatial layout, the proposed layout is successful in reducing d_{xymax} . Contrary to this, it can be found that the Mirror-reversal layout has a larger value of d_{zmax} than the Reference model due to the torsional deformation of the sub-beam. However, it can be considered that the difference between them is small, and the proposed layout has structural feasibility close to the conventional system. An improvement of torsional stiffness, e.g., connecting with each sub-beam, can reduce such torsional displacement.

Fig. 25 depicts the in-plane deformation behaviour in each layout. It indicates that the sub-beams in the Planar parallel layout and the Diagonal spatial layout deform rotationally due to the basic unit's rotations. Contrary to this, the sub-beams in the Mirror reversal layout deforms translationally on the x - y plane. It can be considered that the proposed layout enables improving the in-plane deformation mode by using the mirror-reversal relationship. The arrangement of additional members, as dotted lines in Fig. 25, is effective for restraining the sub-beams from each other to reduce further lateral displacement.

(a) $d_{\max} = 0.70$ mm, $d_{xy\max} = 0.46$ mm, and $d_{z\max} = 0.69$ mm (b) $d_{\max} = 0.69$ mm, $d_{xy\max} = 0.61$ mm, and $d_{z\max} = 0.55$ mm

(c) $d_{\max} = 0.75$ mm, $d_{xy\max} = 0.50$ mm, and $d_{z\max} = 0.72$ mm (d) $d_{\max} = d_{z\max} = 0.56$ mm and $d_{xy\max} = 0.0$ mm

Figure 24: Distribution of deformation (magnified by 500 times): (a) Planar parallel layout, (b) Diagonal spatial layout, and (c) Mirror-reversal layout.

Figure 25: Comparison of deformation behaviour in each layout.

Fig. 26 depicts the construction procedure of DS in the Mirror-reversal layout. As shown in Fig. 26, it can be considered that the basic unit requires temporary support for stabilization in the intermediate construction phases due to in-plane rotational displacements of basic units, as well as the construction of the basic unit. Although DS improves manufacturability due to comprising universal elements, the results in this paper show that it is challenging to construct the structure as Wachsmann's hypothetical image (Fig. 3 (b)), and more temporary materials are required than in the conventional rigid frame structure due to its rotational arrangement.

Figure 26: Construction procedure of DS in Mirror-reversal layout.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper validates DS, which was proposed by Wachsmann, and presents an updated design methodology for obtaining a geometry close to the DS with structural and constructible feasibility. Firstly, we reproduced DS by using 3D CAD software. Through observation, the need for improvement in the joints between upper and lower universal elements is confirmed. Further, we propose a revised algorithm and an assembling procedure. The linear static FE analysis is conducted to investigate the mechanical properties of DS. The effectiveness of the proposed algorithm and the assembling procedure is analyzed by comparing the DS geometry obtained by the previous studies and conventional structural systems. The main conclusions of this paper are summarized as follows.

1) Through reproducing Wachsmann's geometry, it

can be confirmed that joints that connect upper and lower universal elements need to be updated. The proposed algorithm provides sufficient joinery. Through quantitative measurements of the void, DS has enough space to include equipment, such as piping, compared to the conventional rigid frame structures, where piping cannot penetrate without "damaging" the structural element. The proposed assembling procedure improves the temporary support for the sub-beams.

2) Through the results of the linear static FE analysis, the practical feasibility of DS's geometries, which are obtained by the revised algorithm and assembling procedure, can be confirmed. As for the FE analysis for the basic unit, it can be confirmed that the revised algorithm is effective in obtaining sufficient joint areas for universal elements. As seen in the numerical results, the proposed layout's displacement is approximately equal to the Planar parallel layout. Furthermore, compared to the Reference model, it has a larger vertical displacement due to the torsional deformation. However, it can be considered that the difference between them is small. The proposed layout has a structural feasibility close to the conventional structural system.

3) While comprising a single member enhances the improvement of fabrication efficiency, the results in this paper indicate that more temporary construction materials, such as temporary supports and braces, are needed compared to the conventional rigid frame structure. There are many challenges to constructing DS using existing construction methods, and it is necessary to propose new construction methods that can also reduce the amount of temporary materials.

Although we were able to provide structural feasibility in this paper, it should be mentioned for further practical applications that this study needs numerical analysis considering nonlinearity or physical experiment to investigate more detailed structural properties, such as the structural stability or collapse mechanism subjected to external disturbance.

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